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IMPLEMENTATION OF A CONTEXT-AWARE ROUTING MECHANISM IN AN INEXPENSIVE STANDALONE COMMUNICATION SYSTEM FOR DISASTER SCENARIOS

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ABSTRACT

Natural disasters often destroy and disrupt communication infrastructures that hinder the utilization of disaster applications and services needed by emergency responders. During these circumstances an implementation of a standalone communication system (SCS) that serves as an alternative communication platform for vital disaster management activities is essential. In this study, we present a design and implementation of an SCS realized using an inexpensive microcontroller platform. Specifically, the study employed Raspberry Pi (RPi) devices as rapidly deployable relay nodes designed with a context-aware routing mechanism. The routing mechanism decides the most efficient route to send messages or disseminate information in the network by utilizing a context-aware factor (CF) calculated using several context information such as delivery probability and link quality. Moreover, with the use of this context information, the proposed scheme aims to reduce communication delay and overhead in the network commonly caused by resource contention of users. The performance of the proposed SCS was evaluated in a small-area case-scenario deployment using a messaging application and web-based monitoring service. Additionally, a simulation-based performance analysis of the proposed context-aware routing mechanism applied to an urban area map was also conducted. Furthermore, in the simulation, the proposed scheme was compared to the most commonly used Flooding and AODV schemes for SCS. Results show a high delivery probability, faster delivery time (low latency) and reduced message overhead when using the proposed approach compared with the other routing schemes.

KEYWORDS

Standalone communication systems, disaster communication systems, context-aware routing

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CONTEXT-AWARE ENERGY CONSERVING ROUTING ALGORITHM FOR INTERNET OF THINGS

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ABSTRACT

Internet of Things (IoT) is the fast-growing technology, mostly used in smart mobile devices such as notebooks, tablets, personal digital assistants (PDA), smart phones, etc. Due to its dynamic nature and the limited battery power of the IoT enabled smart mobile nodes, the communication links between intermediate relay nodes may fail frequently, thus affecting the routing performance of the network and also the availability of the nodes. Existing algorithm does not concentrate about communication links and battery power/energy, but these node links are a very important factor for improving the quality of routing in IoT. In this paper, Context-aware Energy Conserving Algorithm for routing (CECA) was proposed which employs QoS routing metrics like Inter-Meeting Time and residual energy and has been applied to IoT enabled smart mobile devices using different technologies with different microcontroller which resulted in an increased network lifetime, throughput and reduced control overhead and the end to end delay. Simulation results show that, with respect to the speed of the mobile nodes from 2 to 10m/s, CECA increases the network lifetime, thereby increasing the average residual energy by 11.1% and increasing throughput there by reduces the average end to end delay by 14.1% over the Energy-Efficient Probabilistic Routing (EEPR) algorithm. With respect to the number of nodes increases from 10 to 100 nodes, CECA algorithms increase the average residual energy by 16.1 % reduces the average end to end delay by 15.9% and control overhead by 23.7% over the existing EEPR.

KEYWORDS

Energy conserving, smart mobile devices, Routing, Residual energy, Inter-meeting time.

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FAST PACKETS DELIVERY TECHNIQUES FOR URGENT PACKETS IN EMERGENCY APPLICATIONS OF INTERNET OF THINGS

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ABSTRACT

Internet of Things (IoT) has been receiving a lot of interest around the world in academia, industry and telecommunication organizations. In IoT, many constrained devices can communicate with each other which generate a huge number of transferred packets. These packets have different priorities based on the applications which are supported by IoT technology. Emergency applications such as calling an ambulance in a car accident scenario need fast and reliable packets delivery in order to receive an immediate response from a service provider. When a client sends his request with specific requirements, fast and reliable return contents (packets) should be fulfilled, otherwise, the network resources may be wasted and undesirable circumstances may be counted. Content-Centric Networking (CCN) has become a promising network paradigm that satisfies the requirements of fast packets delivery for emergency applications of IoT. In this paper, we propose fast packets delivery techniques based on CCN for IoT environment, these techniques are suitable for urgent packets in emergency applications that need fast delivery. The simulation results show how the proposed techniques can achieve high throughput, a large number of request messages, fast response time and a low number of lost packets in comparison with the normal CCN.

KEYWORDS

Internet of Things, Content-Centric Networking, emergency applications, data delivery, real-time packets.

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THE PERFORMANCE OF CONVOLUTIONAL CODING BASED COOPERATIVE COMMUNICATION: RELAY POSITION AND POWER ALLOCATION ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Wireless communication faces adversities due to noise, fading, and path loss. Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) systems are used to overcome individual fading effect by employing transmit diversity. Duo to user single-antenna, Cooperation between at least two users is able to provide spatial diversity. This paper presents the evaluation of the performances of the Amplify and Forward (AF) cooperative system for different relay positions using several network topologies over Rayleigh and Rician fading channel. Furthermore, we present the performances of AF cooperative system with various power allocation. The results show that cooperative communication with convolutional coding shows an outperformance compared to the non-convolutional, which is a promising solution for high data-rate networks such as (WSN), Ad hoc, (IoT), and even mobile networks. When topologies are compared, the simulation shows that, linear topology offers the best BER performance, in contrast when the relay acts as source and the source take the relay place, the analysis result shows that, equilateral triangle topology has the best BER performance and stability, and the system performance with inter-user Rician fading channel is better than the performance of the system with inter-user Rayleigh fading channel.

KEYWORDS

MIMO, AF cooperative, convolutional coding, path loss, power allocation, fading.

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QoS CATEGORIES ACTIVENESS-AWARE ADAPTIVE EDCA ALGORITHM FOR DENSE IOT NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

IEEE 802.11 networks have a great role to play in supporting and deploying of the Internet of Things (IoT). The realization of IoT depends on the ability of the network to handle a massive number of stations and transmissions and to support Quality of Service (QoS). IEEE 802.11 networks enable the QoS by applying the Enhanced Distributed Channel Access (EDCA) with static parameters regardless of existing network capacity or which Access Category (AC) of QoS is already active. Our objective in this paper is to improve the efficiency of the uplink access in 802.11 networks; therefore we proposed an algorithm called QoS Categories Activeness-Aware Adaptive EDCA Algorithm (QCAA AE) which adapts Contention Window (CW) size, and Arbitration Inter-Frame Space Number (AIFSN) values depending on the number of associated Stations (STAs) and considering the presence of each AC. For different traffic scenarios, the simulation results confirm the outperformance of the proposed algorithm in terms of throughput (increased on average 23%) and retransmission attempts rate (decreased on average 47%) considering acceptable delay for sensitive delay services.

KEYWORDS

IoT, IEEE 802.11, EDCA, CW, AIFSN, MAC, QoS

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A MIN-MAX SCHEDULING LOAD BALANCED APPROACH TO ENHANCE ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND PERFORMANCE OF MOBILE ADHOC NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Energy efficiency and traffic management in Mobile Ad hoc Networks (MANETs) is a complex process due to the self-organizing nature of the nodes. Quality of service (QoS) of the network is achieved by addressing the issues concerned with load handling and energy conservation. This manuscript proposes a min-max scheduling (M2S) algorithm for energy efficiency and load balancing (LB) in MANETs. The algorithm operates in two phases: neighbor selection and load balancing. In state selection, the transmission of the node is altered based on its energy and packet delivery factor. In the load balancing phase, the selected nodes are induced by queuing and scheduling the process to improve the rate of load dissemination. The different processes are intended to improve the packet delivery factor (PDF) by selecting appropriate node transmission states. The transmission states of the nodes are classified through periodic remaining energy update; the queuing and scheduling process is dynamically adjusted with energy consideration. A weight-based normalized function eases neighbor selection by determining the most precise neighbor that satisfies transmission and energy constraints. The results of the proposed M2SLB (Min-Max Scheduling Load Balancing) proves the consistency of the proposed algorithm by improving the network throughput, packet delivery ratio and minimizing delay and packet loss by retaining higher remaining energy.

KEYWORDS

Energy Efficiency, Load Balancing, MANET, Packet Delivery Factor, Queuing and Scheduling.

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OPTIMIZATION OF PACKET LENGTH FOR TWO WAY RELAYING WITH ENERGY HARVESTING

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we suggest optimizing packet length for two way relaying with energy harvesting. In the first transmission phase, two source nodes N1 and N2 are transmitting data to each others through a selected relay R. In the second phase, the selected relay will amplify the sum of the signals received signals from N1 and N2. The selected relay amplifies the received signals using the harvested energy from Radio Frequency (RF) signals transmitted by nodes N1 and N2. Finally, N1 will remove, from the relay's signal, its own signal to be able to decode the symbol of N2. Similarly, N2 will remove, from the relay's signal, its own signal to be able to decode the symbol of N1. We derive the outage probability, packet error probability and throughput at N1 and N2. We also optimize packet length to maximize the throughput at N1 or N2.

INDEX TERMS

Cooperative systems, Optimal packet length, Rayleigh fading channels.

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